

ENERGY MODELLING PLATFORM – LATIN AMERICA AND THE CARIBBEAN | 2023

Argentinian Case

Nicolás Thaine

Strategic Planning Department - National Atomic Energy Commission

1. Context

- National population is 46.2 million inhabitants according to the 2022 census.[1]
- GDP: ARS 689.211 Millions at constant 2004 prices. [2]
- As of December 2021, the installed capacity is 42,997 MW (59.1% fossil fuel, 4.1% nuclear, 26.4% hydraulic, and 10.4% from other renewables).[3]
- The proven conventional oil and gas reserves as of December 2021 are 274.0 MMm³ and 171,399 MMm³ respectively. [4]
- The proven unconventional oil and gas reserves as of December 2021 are 177.2 MMm³ and 244,589 MMm³ respectively.[4]

2. Aim

- How does Argentina adapt to different restrictions?
- Do we have the capacity to withstand climatic variations?
- What could be the best combination for the energetic matrix?

Figure 1.

3. Methods & Scenarios

- In this case, the CLEW methodology was used with the Osemosys tool.
- **BAU**: Scenario with the restrictions imposed by the course.
- Scenario B: Renewable generation restricted to 30% of total demand, constant residual capacity of nuclear energy and reduction of CO2 emissions in a linear manner to 2050.
- Scenario C: Scenario B + maintain the hydro capacity of the BAU, population increase, electricity demand, public water demand, decrease in available water, decrease in crop yield.
- The graph shows power generation, cost of power and water demand

4. Results

5. Policy insights, conclusions and future work

- Natural Gas is a fundamental vector for the energy transition.
- Renewable energies are important in mitigating climate change, but without forgetting that there are also known alternatives that we should not stop analyzing.
- There are no globalized solutions that work in the same way for all countries, but each country has to adapt to its reality and resources.
- CLEWs is a fundamental tool to be able to estimate possible adaptation scenarios.

6. References

- [1] Source: Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas y Censos (INDEC)
- [2] Source: INDEC. Dirección Nacional de Cuentas Nacionales.
- [3] <https://www.cnea.gov.ar/nuclea/handle/10665/1911>
- [4] <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/economia/energia/hidrocarburos/reservas-de-petroleo-y-gas>

Contact: Nicolás Thaine nicolasthaine@cnea.gov.ar

A Cost-benefit analysis of Policy, Programs and Projects (C3PO) that is Retrievable, Reusable, Repeatable, Reconstructible, Interoperable and Auditable (u4RIA)